

INTEGRATING LITERATURE WITH ADMINISTRATION AND ECONOMY IN MUKIMI'S LITERARY WORKS

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Annotation: This article discusses the poems and ghazals of Muhammad Aminkhoja Mirzakhoja ugli Mukimi, a renowned poet and thinker of his era. It explores the socio-economic conditions of the 19th and 20th centuries and examines Mukimi's attitudes and critical perspectives on the administration and economy of his time. Additionally, the article analyzes how Mukimi's critical and comic masterpieces and ghazals influenced state administration and the economy in detail.

Key words: Mukimi, his life and work, state administration, literature, economy, economic views, critical thoughts, politics, justice.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются стихи и газели Мухаммада Аминходжи Мирзаходжи угли Муками, известного поэта и мыслителя своей эпохи. В нем исследуются социально-экономические условия XIX и XX веков, а также взгляды и критические взгляды Муками на управление и экономику того времени. Кроме того, в статье подробно анализируется влияние критических и комических шедевров и газелей Муками на государственное управление и экономику.

Ключевые слова: Муками, его жизнь и деятельность, государственное управление, литература, экономика, экономические взгляды, критические мысли, политика, правосудие.

Introduction

Literature is the art of words. It strives to uncover subtle nuances and tones in the human heart and soul, reflecting them through the medium of language. The highest caliber of literary works represents the thoughts, experiences, and aspirations that stir and excite humanity. Just as no two individuals in the world are alike, their emotional experiences are equally unique and diverse. The history of Uzbek literature is replete with masterpieces that skillfully depict the myriad states of the human mind. These literary works have the power to inspire and excite the minds and hearts of contemporary generations, contributing significantly to their spiritual enrichment. Crucially, such literature extends beyond merely enhancing our educational knowledge; it also serves to refine our artistic sensibilities and foster our spiritual maturity.

Among the illustrious figures in Uzbek literature, Muhammad Aminkhoja Mirzakhoja ugli, known by the pen name Mukimi, stands out prominently. Born in Kokand in 1850 into a family of intellectuals, Mukimi was a keen observer of his times. He lived through a period marked by significant social and political upheaval, witnessing firsthand the various transformations within his region. This era of political change and social instability profoundly influenced his work.

Mukimi was not just a poet; he was a thinker and a social critic who adeptly used satire and intellect to address the pressing issues of his time. His literary works often highlighted the prevalent problems of poverty, injustice, and corruption. Through his sharp wit and critical eye, Mukimi turned these societal issues into subjects of his art, using them as a powerful weapon against the adversities of his era. His poems and ghazals, rich with satirical undertones, provided incisive commentary on the political and economic conditions of his society.

Moreover, Mukimi's ability to blend satire with profound intelligence allowed him to present a nuanced critique of the administration and economy of his time. His works did not merely reflect the harsh realities of 19th and 20th-century life but also offered a means to understand and challenge these realities. Through his critical and often comic masterpieces, Mukimi sought to illuminate the flaws within the state administration and economic systems, advocating for social change and justice.

Literature review

Mukimi's poems, enriched with the politics of his time, occupied a deep place in the hearts of the people and resonated with them. He criticized the government's oppressive actions against the people and was not afraid to speak openly about it. His cartoons such as "Maskovchi boy tarifida", "Veksel", "Viktor Boy" and "Tanobchilar" are cries for reforming society, expressing the pain of the oppressed and their frustration with this system of government.

These verses in the comic book "Tariff of the Muscovite Boy" after the accession of Central Asia to Russia, the beginning and development of capitalist relations caused the emergence of rich people who go to Moscow to trade, and this is what it is about.

Here Mukimi moves from universality to particularity, that is, it becomes clearer who this comic exposes. Khodikhoja Eshon was one of the rich people of Kokand at that time, he owned large cotton fields, cotton cleaning factories, stores, and branches of these stores in other regions of Fergana. In addition to the comic strip "The Muscovite Boy on the Tariff", his character, who often mentions this person in his satires "Veksel", "Viktor Boy" and others, revealed new aspects of his character and was wrapped in satire to the public. presented in the case and exposed the class of exploiters, i.e. the class of property owners who use the property and labor of others, as a full representative.

Since the revolution, there have been such agreements between borrowers and lenders, that is, if a person borrows money and cannot repay it within the agreed time period, that is, if he starts working at the expense of his business, his property is confiscated by the moneylenders as collateral, and they "printed" with it and appropriated. Mukimi is talking about this phenomenon that created capitalist relations.

In this satire, we will see these lines and all of us will be speechless from the usury and corruption of those times. The debtor was obliged to pay the specified amount (rate) of money rent as a bribe (usury) to the moneylender and officials. Usury flourished after the introduction of capitalist relations, resulting in increased indebtedness among the local working people. Responsibility is one of the main problems and themes of the literature of these times.

In those times, if he sued someone, the law, i.e. Sharia, made the plaintiff swear an oath to the responsible persons. This issue of oath was one of the worst and unbearable laws of that time. Rich people, big property owners, big landowners used to swear as a weapon to kill ordinary poor local people, many of them, and destroy peasants. That is, with various threats and pressures, they pledged their property worth several times more than their debts as collateral and swore that they would agree to confiscate them if they could not pay off their debts.

Results of research

It would not be an exaggeration to say that these criticisms, wrapped in the garb of open satire, are Mukimi's weapon against the politics of Tsarist Russia. Mukimi's comic books will not bore the reader. Sometimes it makes you laugh, and sometimes it makes you think deeply. The

heroes of his comics are certainly not absent in our time. He was able to quickly enter the hearts of the people through his humorous stories. His simple, easy-to-understand comics reflect real-life events. In the hands of the poet, laughter is not rude laughter or just cheerfulness, small humor, but obstacles to backward progress in life, weaknesses and negative signs in the mind and nature of individuals, ugly character and inappropriate behavior. serves the function of condemnation, rebuke, warning.

Discussion

Mukimi's skillful use of images and metaphors adds depth and poignancy to his political commentary. He describes the suffering and the downtrodden in such a way that every person who reads these poems can stand against such injustices and, of course, fight against them, and feel the hardships of those times in spirit.

Moreover, the influence of Mukimi's poems went beyond the borders of Uzbekistan. His poems, ghazals, and humor have been translated into various languages, especially English, German, Russian, Bengali, and Hindi, and have reached literature lovers all over the world. Scholars and lovers of literature continue to analyze his work, appreciating its historical content, social commentary and economic aspects, political appeal and purely artistic qualities. Koldosh Pardayev, Ghulam Karimov and Said Abdulla are among such enthusiasts.

At a time when Uzbekistan is trying to make its own way in the world literary scene, Mukimi's critical poems and ghazals remain a source of inspiration. His political poetry serves as a beacon that reminds us of the power of opposition and the importance of fighting for social justice.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the poems and ghazals he wrote down are not just writings, but they are an eternal mirror reflecting the constant struggle between oppression, tyranny, corruption and justice and solidarity. Although a century has passed since the creation of these masterpieces, his verses still retain their power and remind us that the struggle for justice and responsibility requires constant effort. As mentioned above, Mukimi's legacy serves as a beacon, that is, language and literature are used as weapons against lies and injustice. urges not to hesitate. Studying the way of life and creativity of this great person not only gives pleasure, but also cognitive knowledge and new knowledge. As a result of each re-search, other new aspects will emerge and ensure that we have the right attitude to justice and public policy of the youth.

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